

COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT TEST METHOD FOR THIN LAMINATES

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Keywords: Compression After Impact, Thin laminates, Residual strength, Device, Test method.

ABSTRACT

Compression After Impact (CAI) test has a strong interest in the aviation and aerospace industry, because a low velocity impact can cause a relevant decrease in the compression strength of composite structures. Besides, delaminations are particularly dangerous because of their difficult detectability. Furthermore, the structural components of many aviation and aerospace applications have thin thickness, of about 2mm. Unfortunately, the CAI standard prevents from testing laminates with less than 4mm of thickness, because buckling appears in the specimen. In a previous work, the authors developed a CAI device to test thin laminates.

In this work the thickness range of laminates that can be tested at compression after impact was analysed, ensuring that the stress state is uniaxial and buckling not appear. Undamaged and damaged laminates of different thicknesses were tested, using two different devices: the ASTM D7137 device and the developed device. Furthermore, the problem was modelled to determine the buckling stress for different configurations. When the residual strength is higher than the buckling stress, the laminate should not be tested with that device. The simulations of composite laminates with and without damage show that the developed device can be used to test thinner laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Compression After Impact (CAI) test has a strong interest in the aviation and aerospace industry, since a low velocity impact can cause a relevant decrease in the compression strength. The interlaminar damage or delaminations are particularly dangerous because of their difficult detectability. The structural components of many aviation and aerospace applications have thin thickness, of about 2mm. Nowadays, CAI standards, as ASTM D7137 [1], employs a laminate thickness greater than 4 mm.

In the scientific literature, there are several proposals for the CAI test of thin specimens [2-4]. For example, Sjöblom and Hwang [2] proposed the use of a steel anti-buckling support with a central hole but this device needs narrow specimens with end tabs. Sanchez-Saez et al. [3] proposed another CAI device with four anti-buckling plates placed on both sides of the specimen leaving a cut-out so as not to interfere with the damage. Both devices were designed for testing specimens of different dimensions from ASTM, making the comparison of the results difficult. In a previous work, the

authors developed a CAI device to test thin laminates [4]. In this device, specimen stability was improved by a support structure, with a set of vertical ribs that increase the buckling load.

In this paper, the minimum laminate thickness that can be tested with ASTM device and developed device is studied in order to estimate their range of applicability. Undamaged and damaged laminates of different thicknesses were analysed. The problem is numerical modelled to determine the buckling stress in the different configurations tested. This value is compared with the residual strength of undamaged and damaged to determine that failure mode appear first: buckling or compression breakage. The simulations of the composite laminates with and without damage show the potential of the developed device.

2 DESCRIPTION OF CAI DEVICES USED

Two CAI devices were used in this work: ASTM D7137 device and authors' proposed device. A brief description of both devices is presented in this section.

The device determined by ASTM D7137 "Standard Test Method for Compressive Residual Strength Properties of Damaged Polymer Matrix Composite Plates" [1] supports the side edges and fixes the upper and lower edges. The ASTM device was chosen because it is the most widely used and it is the reference for major companies such as Airbus or Boeing. Unfortunately, this CAI standard prevents from testing laminates with less than 4mm of thickness, because buckling appears in the specimen, as it is shown in Fig. 1 for laminates with 1.472mm of thickness tested according to ASTM D7137.

Figure 1: Stress-strain curves for 1.472mm-thick undamaged specimens tested with ASTM device.

On the other hand, the device developed by the authors [4] delays global buckling, stabilizing the specimen and, therefore, increasing the buckling load. The laminate should not reach the critical buckling load before the CAI failure occurs. Furthermore, the CAI device was designed according to several characteristics such as the no interference with the damage (to allow the local buckling of sub-laminates and the progression of the delamination), security, robustness, accurate alignment of the applied load, minor friction, device weight, ease of use, installation and industrialization.

It consists of a support structure with a set of vertical protuberant elements. These ribs stabilize the specimen, decreasing the buckling dimension of the test sample. A free space was left cutting the central rib, so there is no interference with the damage. A patent of this device was published: PCT / ES2012 / 070 087 [5]. The developed device and a detail of the vertical protuberant elements are displayed in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Developed CAI device and a detail of the protuberant elements.

The developed device was validated by comparing the results of CAI tests with those obtained using the ASTM device. A total of 64 specimens of 4.416 mm thickness (thickness recommended by the ASTM standard), undamaged and impacted at five different energy levels, were mechanical tested. Fig. 3 presents the residual strength obtained by the ASTM device and the developed device. Similar residual strength was obtained by both devices for the standard thickness for all impact energy levels.

Figure 3: Residual strength of specimen with 4.416 mm of thickness with both devices for several impact energy levels [4].

3 ANALYSIS OF UNDAMAGED LAMINATES

3.1 Undamaged laminates test results

Laminates with three different thicknesses (1.472, 2.944 and 4.416mm) were tested using a quasi-isotropic lay-up $[(45, 0, -45, 90)_n]_s$. The material used for the tests is AS4 /8552, composed of carbon fibre with epoxy resin. This is considered as reference configuration. The 0° direction is considered parallel to the direction of the applied load.

The comparison of the test results obtained by both devices is shown in Fig. 4. It is found that for specimens thicker than 4mm the results are very similar (differences lower than 5%), regardless of the test device. However, the residual strength for thin specimens estimated using the developed device is clearly greater than the residual strength obtained by the standard device. This difference is around 50% for approximately 3mm-thick-laminates or even 75% for 1.5mm-thick-laminates. This is because the specimen buckles before using the ASTM device than when it is supported by the proposed device.

Moreover, it is shown that the compression strength for the reference configuration is around 416MPa.

Figure 4: Experimental results of undamaged specimens with several thicknesses [4].

Despite having checked the highest strength values obtained by the developed device versus the standard one, the lowest residual strength obtained for specimens of about 1.5mm thickness, leads to the need of assessing the valid limit thickness of the solution.

3.2 Buckling analysis and limit thickness definition

Buckling load of undamaged laminates was numerically calculated in order to estimate the limit thickness for which the support device is valid. A bi-dimensional model in Abaqus/Standard ("Linear Perturbation, Buckle") was developed. Both devices were modelled introducing boundary conditions to the specimen, restricting some nodes movements. The displacement in the perpendicular direction and the rotations in an upper and lower zone were restricted, in order to simulate the ASTM device. Furthermore, the lateral edges are also supported in the perpendicular direction to the laminate. On the bottom of the specimen, a zero displacement in the longitudinal direction was imposed showing the action of the lower plate. A distributed load of 100N / mm was introduced at the top. On the other hand, the effect of the new device was modelled in the same way, but also representing the supports provided by the vertical ribs.

The specimen thickness was changed to study different cases modifying the ply thickness, but maintaining a quasi-isotropic laminate [45, 0, -45, 90]_s.

Figure 5: Buckling with the standard device of a specimen of 1.472mm.

Figure 6: Buckling with the developed device of a specimen of 1.472mm.

Critical buckling load is calculated through the first eigenvalue obtained by Abaqus for each specimen thickness. Figs. 5 and 6 show the numerical buckling results for thin laminates (1.472mm) with both devices. The graphical results are compared in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Critical buckling stress depending on the thickness for each of the studied device.

Fig. 7 shows that the buckling stress of the laminate with developed device is much greater than the corresponding with the ASTM device for a wide range of thicknesses. Moreover, the experimental compression strength of the quasi-isotropic laminate is indicated with an horizontal line in this figure

(416 MPa). Such compression strength is also dependent on the thickness [6], but it is assumed constant since the variation will be small as long as the laminate has not buckled before failure.

The specimens whose buckling load is above the compression strength can be tested with each device. According to Fig. 6, the limit thickness with the ASTM device is estimated to be about 3.75mm for the reference configuration, whereas the developed device allows testing undamaged laminates with only 1.84mm. This thickness is significantly smaller than the thickness that enables the standard device.

The limit thickness is dependent on both the material and the stacking sequence, so it would be necessary to study the specific limits for other configurations. For example, testing samples with the following laminate $[45, 0_2, -45, 90, 0]_s$, a compressive strength of 447 MPa is obtained. The critical buckling stress obtained with the developed device was approximately 600MPa, but 154 MPa are obtained using the standard device. As it was expected, a laminate with more 0° plies has a higher critical buckling load, but also a greater strength. Then, this configuration could be tested with the proposed device but not with the ASTM device.

4 ANALYSIS OF DAMAGED LAMINATES

After analyzing the behavior of specimens without damage as an extreme case, the study of the applicability of both devices to test impacted specimens was carried out. This damage due to impact will affect both residual strength and buckling load and, therefore, it will affect the thickness limits of application of the devices.

4.1 Damaged laminates test results

Specimens with the same configuration were tested but, this time, they are impacted at E_{BVID} (Barely Visible Impact Damage energy). This energy was estimated in [4], being 9 J for the samples of 1.472 mm, 22 J for 2.944mm and 34 J for 4.416mm. The results of compression after impact for three thicknesses are shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: CAI experimental results of specimens with different thicknesses impacted at E_{BVID} .

The estimated residual strength by the developed device remains substantially constant for the three thicknesses tested. The variation from the results with standard thickness is 10% for 2.944mm and 0.3% for the thickness of 1.472mm. On the other hand, the residual strength estimated by the standard device varies relative to the standardized thickness 7% for the intermediate thickness and 36% for the thinner. Therefore, noting the results for thin damaged specimens (Fig. 8), it is detected that when they were tested with ASTM device they had buckled before failure. This buckling was confirmed through the measure of gauges positioned on opposite sides, as it is shown in Fig. 9. Meanwhile the developed device can be used to estimate the CAI residual strength for thicknesses of 1.472mm.

Figure 9: Strains gauges in a thin specimen (1.472mm) impacted at E_{BVID} during the CAI test with the standard device.

4.2 Buckling analysis and limit thickness definition

A similar numerical model was used to estimate the buckling stress in the case of damage laminates. A simple approximation to reproduce the damage generated by the impact was employed, modelling the damage as a circular hole in the centre of the laminate [7]. Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show the buckling obtained by Abaqus with both devices. In Fig. 12, the numerical results are shown for a laminate of 1.472mm with holes of different diameters.

Figure 10: Buckling of a specimen of 1.472mm with damage (R=15mm) tested with the ASTM device.

Figure 11: Buckling of a specimen of 1.472mm with damage (R=15mm) tested with the developed device.

Figure 12: Critical buckling stress of specimens of 1.472mm with damage of different sizes.

As happened with the undamaged laminates, the buckling load of the damaged laminates tested with the developed device is greater than the estimated with the ASTM device for different damage levels. In the latter case, the buckling stress does not change substantially with damage; whereas in the case of the results obtained with the developed device higher values than without damage were observed (Fig. 12). Therefore, if the failure value with damage is compared with the buckling value without damage, the analysis is still conservative. Knowing this, the device use is considered right as long as buckling occurs above about 200MPa (approximately experimental residual strength of damage laminates impacted at E_{BVID}). Thus, looking at Fig. 7 again, damaged laminates up to 1.2mm could be tested.

The device is optimized to test composite laminates impacted at E_{BVID} , although the concept is adaptable to other damage levels or geometries. For a specimen with no impact or very little damage, the ribs could be closer together to test smaller thicknesses. The distance between ribs is a compromise between the minimum allowable thickness and no-interference with damage and, therefore, it will be chosen depending on the configuration tested.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The device developed to test thin laminates in a previous work prevents the global buckling in the damaged specimen, ensuring that the failure is due to compression. The residual strength of laminates over 4mm has been proved to be very similar regardless of the test device. On the other hand, the results reveal a high improvement testing thin laminates with the developed device.

The application range of this device depends on the material, stacking sequence and impact energy. The specimens whose buckling load is above the failure load could be tested with that CAI device. The distance between ribs is a compromise between the minimum allowable thickness and no-damage-interference.

Given the reference configuration, the limit thickness to test with the ASTM device has been estimated as approximately 3.75mm for undamaged specimens, whereas the developed device allows testing laminates with 1.84mm of thickness. Since damaged laminate residual strength is lower, damaged specimens of 1.2mm thickness (reference configuration) could be tested with the developed device.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge FIDAMC and University Carlos III of Madrid for their cooperation in this research and development.

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